

ROLE OF CULTURAL HERITAGE RESOURCES TO SUSTAIN TOURISM PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

Current research is designed to investigate what triggering the tourism performance of Toba Caldera as Unesco Global Geopark & Earth Heritage, North Sumatera, Indonesia. Proposing research hypotheses to assess the relationship among conceptual model such as the impact of Attitude towards Sustainable Tourism Strategy (ATSTS), Destination Branding Strategy (DBS), Strategy Awareness (SA) on Tourism Performance (TP) and Cultural Heritage Resources (CHR) as intervening variable. This research based on survey. Questionnaires were distributed through google form and personal email, purposive sampling technique with non-probability used and international tourist as well as domestics administered as research population, and 500 questionnaires were distributed and 380 were return with 360 were valid for further analysis. The quantitative deductive causal approach was use to asses and verify the relationship among hypotheses with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM with AMOS 24). Statistical output described that Attitude towards Sustainable Tourism Strategy showed the significant impact on Tourism Performance directly as well as Cultural Heritage Resources, secondly, Destination Branding Strategy was proven as the antecedent of Tourism Performance. Lastly, the Strategy Awareness also has indirect significant impact on Tourism Performance.

Keywords: Attitude towards Sustainable Tourism Strategy, Destination Branding Strategy, Strategy Awareness, Tourism Performance and Cultural Heritage Resources.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is the biggest industry in the world, and also one of the crucial factors in times of peace that moves people worldwide. Hence, either as an expression or media of globalization, tourism has a deep meaning in every aspect of human life, economy, environment, material, social and cultural trend (Ryan, 2005; Washington, 2013; Ramaano, 2021a). This marks it as the ideal lens for exploring the core themes in contemporary social anthropology, such as locality, identity and alterity, political economics, development, heritage, representation, imagination, commodification; and global circulation of people, objects, ideas, and images. As such, there is a globally embedded requisite to arrange tourism as a source of profit and national income; such require a merging of cultural curiosity in the tourism development dimension (Wang, 2016).

Hence, if it is seen from this perspective, tourism is not only a type of journey, but also a complex social field that unites the world, consisting of various actors, institutions, activities, and overlapping-intersecting interaction mode, with forms of other global interconnection (Bruner, 2010; Christie et al., 2014; Lew, 2014). An updated World Bank report, "Tourism in Africa: Harnessing Tourism for Improved Growth and Livelihoods," stated that nations in Africa could compete with other tourist-rich regions in the world if they could effectively plan and integrate tourism into their economy (Washington, 2013). Nations worldwide have

received profit in tourism alongside the growth of global arrivals (Bruner, 2010; Lew, 2014). According to Washington (2013), from the year 1980 to 2000, arrivals in Pacific Asia have grown from 3% (1980) to 5% (2010).

To close this gap, the report demanded that the African government cooperate with its private sectors in surmounting the obstacles, such as terrain access and visa regulation to expand the tourism opportunities, alter the business climate, and encourage the creation of jobs especially for women and youngsters. “The mountain range, savannah, and the African river, as well as cultural events like music, dance, and festivals are far above the natural assets found in other regions.”

Therefore, the relationship between nature preservation, cultural heritage and tourism development complete one another (Kumar, 2017). Consequently, along with those natural attributes, tourism played a big part in development. As such, tourism needs to be integrated into the economic structure and the government of each country, and also seen as the welfare for all, starting with the president to the ministers to the general public. Tourism in Africa is the first World Bank report to perform an inclusive investigation about tourism in the entirety of Sub-Saharan South Africa (SSA); and urge practical steps based on the evidence that unleashed the power of Economy and the development of this sector all over the continent. As such, this shows that how Botswana, Cape Verde, Namibia, South Africa, and Tanzania, among the other nations, have a great potential for tourism expansion in the past years and thought that many SSA countries are in the verge of tourism success (Washington, 2013; Christie et al., 2014).

For Indonesia cases (Toba Caldera Enesco Global Geopark Heritage, North Sumatera), some famous international tourist destination such as Toba Caldera Geopark, Geosites, Geological Heritage, Sibaganding Mesozoic Limestone. Those sites enrich the cultural heritages in the areas. For more details, see the following Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Toba Caldera Geopark, Geosites, Geological Heritage, Sibaganding Mesozoic Limestone

Besides cultural heritages, this destination is also well-known for its traditional welcoming dances, those traditional dances are existing around Toba Lake. The different tribes have the different traditional dances though the tribes are still categorized shared the same ancestor. Some dances are worth to mention such as Tor-Tor Dance, Simalungun Dance, Piso Surit Dance, Fak-Fak Dance. For more details, as illustrated at Fig. 2

Huibin et al. (2012) thought that in accelerating tourism growth, the general tourist attraction aspect is cultural heritage that is bountiful, appropriate and special. A grandeur such as this has a great potential to be a tourist attraction with a long lasting charm and luxury. For this purpose, Coccossis (2016) reminds us that tourism is a multi-facet socio-economy based on the contemporary needs of the people and developed for recreation and entertainment.

Therefore, in order to increase the rest for cultural heritage and education, South Africa (1996) alongside White Paper on Tourism and Development acknowledged the might of tourism in empowering their people especially the ones that are disadvantaged and marginalized. With a bountiful cultural resource and rich tourism, bear witness regarding the empowerment scheme and the necessity which is referred to before. As such, the locals could depend their income on the tourism strategy that could potentially be effective in that region. However, Butler and Ivanovic (2016) saw that despite the recent development of some tourism strategies in South Africa, the progress of cultural heritage tourism has yet to achieve the desirable level. This, in turn, is consistent with Myers et al. (2016) about the essence of the practice of integrated web-

based heritage management for the continuous widespread growth initiative.

Figure 2: Traditional Dances of Batak Toba (Tor-Tor), Simalungun (Simalungun Dance), Batak Karo (Piso Surit) and Batak Fak-Fak (Fak-Fak Dance)

The problem formulations adhere to the fact that regardless of the abundance of fascinating cultural resources and heritage in the study region during the research by (Ramaano, 2021b) stated that resources do not seem to be used optimally to empower the people in the area. Therefore, the question for the research is: How do we increase the usage of heritage-oriented cultural resources in a study region as a livelihood and sustainability; all while strengthening the steps for community development? As such, this revolves around the implicit outlooks regarding the utilization of cultural heritage resources to advance the livelihoods of the people. Hence, they needed the framework of continuous tourism advancement on the potential of cultural heritage resources in fixing the government policy towards cultural resource management. This study suggests that in identifying said potential resources and its usage, one could advocate an appropriate significant step in tourism and a scheme for the development of the people in the study area.

The things mentioned above must be done alongside a cultural resource-based public policy, cultural heritage tourism and community development. The last mentioned will become a benchmark and reference for other village communities both inside and outside the continent who have an abundance of cultural heritage, development of local economy and continuous achievements (Ramaano, 2021b).

The different traditional house for each tribe also enrich the cultural heritages. As shown at Fig. 3, the typical of traditional houses tailor the tourist destination.

Traditional House: Batak Toba

Traditional House – Simalungun

Traditional House – Batak Karo

Traditional House – Pak-Pak

Figure 3: Traditional House of Batak Toba, Simalungun, Batak Karo and Batak Fak-Fak

Current research is conducted to investigate the determinant factors of tourism destination performance in Toba Lake. Proposing three independent variables (Attitude toward Sustainable Tourism Strategy, Destination Branding, Strategy Awareness) and Cultural Heritage Resource Managed as intervening variable.

LITERATURE REVIEWS

Hypotheses Development

The Relationship among Attitude towards Sustainable Tourism Strategy (AtSTS), Cultural Heritage Resources (CHR) and Tourism Performance (TP)

Various promotes constant tourism development to democratize access to management, as well as economic and social benefits obtained from tourism. The new national Political Constitution mandates the decentralization, territorial autonomy, and coordination between the private, public, cooperative, and community sectors. Furthermore, tourism must be supported by social, environmental, and cultural inclusion, distribution, synergy, reciprocity, balance and responsibility. These points allowed the reconciliation of individual and general interests with the means of Good Living. Tourism is commonly arranged by basic principles related to the

guidelines and instructions of Country which are: social inclusion, equal chances, equality in income distribution and law enforcement, and natural resource preservation: diversity in culture and economy; social synergy and institutions between communities, private and public in the process of decision-making, integrality and competition. Equality in chances and income distribution in accordance to the freedom of business and responsibility for competition, social, environment, and culture.

Findings confirmed that in many case, tourism is an activity inspired by high political ideals, and not a power based on mercy and instruction of market power and private entity. Organic tourism development relates to the concept of community self-actualization. Identifying the massive potential in tourism which is inherent to the low influence and specialty of tourism towards the development of local communities (Lima Cortez & Sinclair, 2010). Relationships and supporting factors showing the current situation of tourism and latent was mostly criticized. Many cities were enriched with tourism potential and in need of appropriate tourism plan to be of profit for the locals (Ramaano, 2021b).

Research showed how the existence of resources and abilities, both tangible and intangible of the people being merge and exploited in a tourism initiative through a strategy that puts community sustainability as the main goal. This process leads to the emersion of competitive advantage promoting the continuity of the people's lifestyles, ensuring a long lasting rural tourism initiative approach (Artal-Tur, Briones-Peñalver, Bernal-Conesa, & Martínez-Salgado, 2019). Biodiversity conservation, sustainable attitude, climate change, protected area, satisfaction and environment management are the main motor themes in the research period. Additionally, the four fields for the future educational investigation are identified and discussed: sustainable attitude and environment preservation; consumption, demands and economic growth; tourism strategy and development; and rural tourism, poverty, ethics and education (Molina-Collado, Santos-Vijande, Gómez-Rico, & Madera, 2022).

Classifying the tangible and intangible cost and benefits because of the tourists' walkability and triple bottom line trade-off experienced by tourists and the people. Breaking new grounds by reviewing the result of triple bottom line from tourist walkability towards the community's quality of life. The government's policy as a mediation variable and national culture and tourists' individual personality and the community as a moderation variable is being discussed.

A destination alongside the hotel and tourism industry could engineer various strategies to make a sustainable industry. A practical solution recommended by the contributors really helped in sharing good practices and in identifying the potential roadblocks in doing said practice (Balouei Jamkhaneh, Shahin, & Shahin, 2022).

Research on sustainable rural tourism could very much support the cultivation of rural destination and give significant contributions towards the continuous development of the tourism industry generally, and especially towards village economy, sustainable tourism practice contributing towards preventing poverty, provide decent jobs and ensure economy growth, help reducing the gap, protect cultural heritage and global environment, promote

responsible consumption and productions and last but not least, this destination shows that development can only happen when a partnership is forged (Yeap & Liow, 2023)

Some destinations are still focused on attracting more tourists from the International Market while the others are in a more mature stage, focusing their work towards tourism flow management (Spencer et al., 2023). This last example supported the approach that in developing a tourism strategy. they must start with the destination needs, and the locals must contribute directly and fully in the tourism strategy (Coroş, Gică, Yallop, & Moiescu, 2017). Initiatives like this could support the data and strong evidence based decision making in tourism, as well as help overcome doubts and misunderstandings surrounding the feelings of the people (Araújo, 2021; Gica, Coroş, Moiescu, & Yallop, 2021). Current study proposed the following hypotheses:

H1a: The Higher Level on Attitude towards Sustainable Tourism Strategy, the Better Cultural Heritage Resources

H1b: The higher level on Attitude towards Sustainable Tourism Strategy, the higher Tourism Performance

The Relationship among Destination Branding (DB), Cultural Heritage Resources (CHR), and Tourism Performance (TP)

Collecting terms and concepts from multiple external and internal sources are enough to start the taxonomy development process. One of the key components of Integrated Museum and Archive System taxonomy is its ability to show the broad picture of all the resources possessed by the National Heritage Board, apart from its original institution (Sattar Chaudhry & Pei Jiun, 2005).

This finding elucidates the obstacles faces by users in using the digital cultural heritage resources in New Zealand. They also highlight the necessities and features as well as user characteristics that they most desire in digital cultural heritage resources (Dorner, Li Liew, & Ping Yeo, 2007). A cultural place promotes the development of soft descriptions of regional cultural heritage and help the discovery of relations to help increase value construction skills. Other than that, story-telling through face-to-face interactive user really helps in utilizing and spreading the knowledge taken from cultural space and encourage the release of regional cultural heritage values. This way, a path with cultural value attached to cultural heritage as its core can be established, and its preservation achieved (Liu, Pan, & Han, 2023).

This study reveals the variety of cultural sources and heritage; however, with an implication that tourism welfare is currently lacking in the people's livelihood status. As such, there is a need for a tourism strategy with a potential in cultural heritage resources to empower the locals in the study region (Ramaano, 2021a). Test study shows that the tool proposed may be able to discern whether, how and how far the function of contemporary commercial from certain immovable cultural heritage element can contribute to the continuous local development and whether and how far cultural sustainability from a certain cultural heritage could be confirmed.

In the case of heirloom being re-adopted as a commercial function, there are some cultural effect differences. The presence of tourism and only being aware to it in a region is not enough to create a socio-cultural function in multiple aspects. This kind of heritage isn't being used to its utmost potential (Niemczewska, 2020). The hypotheses proposed are as follows:

H2a: The Better Destination Branding, the Better Cultural Heritage Resources Managed

H2b: The Better Destination Branding, The higher Tourism Performance

The Relationship between Strategy Awareness (SA) and Cultural Heritage Resources (CHR)

Findings supported the main differential effect at strategic awareness between the border personnel based on the source of message, whether top management or middle management. Interestingly, it sees that there's an interaction effect between two sources soon to be used as a dominant information source for border personnel. (Davis, Allen, & Dibrell, 2012). This finding confirmed a high-leveled consensus stating that the main food risk reducer is: travel information, staff training in security assurance, legislation, and risk prevention protocol. This finding also showed a significant limitation in the information offered by restaurants, organizations and tourist destinations and the negative effect on tourist experience and reputation of a certain destination (Fuentes-Moraleda, Muñoz-Mazón, Santiago-Rincón, & Orea-Giner, 2021). This study analyzes how tourism industry in active agribusiness made it possible for local areas to be improved as well as improving and strengthening strategy and sustainable choice for the organization and customers, especially in the context of post pandemic era change (Badia, Galeone, & Shini, 2023).

While a female director is a significant boost in performance in the tourism sector, more precisely in the arrival and acceptance of tourists, independent directors are only effective in improving tourist's arrivals. Moreover, moderation analysis shows the ineffectively of the council's policy in increasing the contributions of these directors towards the development of this sector. Other than that, findings reveal the inefficiency of the council meetings (Nimer, Kuzey, & Uyar, 2023). Tourism marketing manager in state and federal institutions are often asked to correct the expense on advertising and marketing program to draw in visitors. The finding in this research gives proof supporting the idea that International Mega-Event motivate searches that would not otherwise occur and to respond to said information search, it is a necessity to reap the benefits from the increasing awareness for being a host to said mega event (Woodside, Ray Spurr, March, & Clark, 2002).

This problem has a wide variety and affects people on different intensity levels and must be handled with different negotiation strategies. However, the difference between problems are observed according to the types of special needs (Deville, Eusébio, & Moura, 2023). The findings from this research shows that cues of content from information quality given by the company has positive effects in increasing awareness towards the destination brand and in turn improves the affective and cognitive images of the company. In the end, the contents of the cue from the information quality given by the company has an effect towards the forming of

conative image through affective and cognitive image of the destination (Ghorbanzadeh, Zakieva, Kuznetsova, Ismael, & Ahmed, 2022).

Data reveals that introducing tourism as a High School subject raises awareness on tourism among the students. The journey pattern of parents whose kids learned about tourism is also affected. Results shows that students who learned about tourism in Middle School will most likely chase after a career in tourism industry (van Niekerk, Okumus, & Saayman, 2013). The marketing strategy used for Dubai Expo 2020 is interesting, varieties, and innovative. Digital marketing is the most used communication channel chosen for marketing purposes either by the higher-ups in Expo 2020 or the tour operator and travel agencies in Dubai. Maximum popularity in terms of usage by the tour operators and travel agencies can be seen in social media marketing channel, such as Facebook. There is a need to develop a clear and separate digital marketing strategy that will affect the consumption attitude of the people involved in Expo 2020 (Haneef & Ansari, 2019). Then, this to propose the following hypothesis:

H3: The More Appropriate Strategy Awareness Executed, The Better Cultural Heritage Resources

The Relationship Cultural Heritage Resources (CHR) and Tourism Performance (TP)

Collecting terms and concepts from multiple external and internal sources are enough to start the taxonomy development process. One of the key components of Integrated Museum and Archive System taxonomy is its ability to show the broad picture of all the resources possessed by the National Heritage Board, apart from its original institution (Sattar Chaudhry & Pei Jiun, 2005). This finding elucidates the obstacles faces by users in using the digital cultural heritage resources in New Zealand. They also highlight the necessities and features as well as user characteristics that they most desire in digital cultural heritage resources (Dorner et al., 2007).

A cultural place promotes the development of soft descriptions of regional cultural heritage and help the discovery of relations to help increase value construction skills. Other than that, storytelling through face-to-face interactive user really helps in utilizing and spreading the knowledge taken from cultural space and encourage the release of regional cultural heritage values. This way, a path with cultural value attached to cultural heritage as its core can be established, and its preservation achieved (Liu et al., 2023).

This study reveals the variety of cultural sources and heritage; however, with an implication that tourism welfare is currently lacking in the people's livelihood status. As such, there is a need for a tourism strategy with a potential in cultural heritage resources to empower the locals in the study region (Ramaano, 2022). There is a chance for studying tourism industry as a chain value and to develop performance management and chain value oriented framework which may enable various players to communicate and coordinate their process and activities in a more mature way. Therefore, it is vital to measure and manage the efficiency and effectivity of the tourism product and service as a whole from the chain value management perspective. Said framework has some implications for practitioners and researchers (Yilmaz & Bititci, 2006).

This study found that the board capital has a positive impact towards the performance of the company in the human capital and social dimension. This study also highlighted two contexts of crucial ownership which are institutional investor and national ownership, forming the Capital-Firm Board Performance Association in China's tourism industry (Yousaf, Ullah, Wang, Junyan, & Rehman, 2021).

Destination competitiveness integrated model (Kim & Shim, 2018) was used. Secondary data from 115 countries available on Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index (TTCI) and other International reports were used. The hypothesized relation is tested through Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). Findings – This study confirmed that core resources, complementary condition, globalization and tourism prices have significantly explained tourism performance. Results has shown the difference in competitiveness level and actual performance between nations, highlighting the specific limitations of the current TDC model and reliability of the TTCI report (Hanafiah & Zulkifly, 2019).

The writers conclude by giving multiple conclusion about the trend and direction of future researches. In relation to the prominent topic, cross-quote, and network analysis giving detailed overview about the origins of literature and its current position. The conclusion is articulated on a theoretical and empirical level (Sainaghi, Baggio, Phillips, & Mauri, 2018). Finding shows that social capital constructions, including structural capital network density, relational capital, and cognitive capital, all of which positively affects knowledge sharing between the UKM in the cluster. This signifies that creating a social capital is vital to improve UKM's competitiveness. This study asserts that knowledge sharing has a positive effect on UKM performance through Innovations (Kim & Shim, 2018).

It is found that while RBV has accepted supports in quantitative and qualitative study, the way researchers use them in quantitative and qualitative research varied greatly in types of resources studied, measuring variables used and in used terminologies/theoretical sub school. To increase the effectivity of RBV as a theoretical base for future researches, its application must be more consistent in various studies, enabling development in integrated theory. Some literary setbacks can be identified, including the practical use of RBV; tautology attached to the RBV based research; the limited number of qualitative research and limited focus in the industrial context other than hotels, not to mention the current plethora of research with Western perspective. These setbacks leads to a suggestion for future researches (Kruesi & Bazelmans, 2022).

This study expands the available literature by investigating the impact of each vital dimensions of sustainable performance – ESG (Environment, Social and Governance) – and review how every dimension will affect financial performance and market value between companies in three different industries related to tourism (transportation, hotel and recreation). Among the three, the hotel industry is recorded to have the highest number of LST obedience, followed by transportation. According to the Agency theory and stakeholders, writers hypothesized that all LST components has a significant positive effect towards the performance of finance and stock market; However, results shows that every dimension has a different impact towards the financial performance and company's market value in the tourism industry (Bodhanwala &

Bodhanwala, 2021). Having reviewed the aforementioned of previous studies, this is to proposed the following hypothesis.

H4: The Better Cultural Heritage Resources Managed, The higher Tourism Performance

To summarize the aforementioned discussion, the conceptual model proposed is as illustrated at fig. 4

Figure 4: Proposed Conceptual Model

Source: Literature Reviewed (2023)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Collection and Sampling

In order to complete the aims of current study, Self-administered questionnaires with survey method was deployed for data collection through google form, personal email. Data was then collected from the local tourist as well as international tourist who had been visited the destination mentioned. 400 hundred questionnaires were return but 360 are valid for further analysis. Data collection was conducted for four months from April to August 2023. Several calls were made in order to increase rate return. Purposive sampling with non-probability sampling was deployed. (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). This is also aligned with (Wilson, 2014) claimed that it is commonly when no opportunity to deploy random sampling. Some criteria are subject to follow by respondents in order to be the sampling, such as revisited attention, concerned on cultural heritages and others considered crucial. The demographic is illustrated at Table 1

Table 1: Respondent's Demographic Profile

Characteristic	Characteristics of Respondent	Total	Percentage
Gender	Female	237	66
	Male	127	34
Age	20-30	15	4,17
	31-40	45	12,5
	41-50	80	23,6
	51 -	120	33,3
Education	College	125	34,7
	Under Graduate	175	48,6
	Post Graduate	25	6,9
	Doctoral	5	1,4
Job Position	House Wife	54	15
	Civil Servant	85	23,6
	Private Sector	124	34,4
	Businessman	50	13,9
	Sales and Marketing	5	1,4
	Others	42	11.7

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Research Instrument Development

Attitude towards Sustainable tourism strategy was measured with 4 items, Destination Branding with 5 items, Strategy Awareness 4 items, Cultural Heritage Resources Managed 5 items, Tourism Performance 4 items. The questionnaire was referred from the previous literatures. The repeated questionnaire have benefit to maintain the reliability and validity (Bryman, 2008).

Common Method Bias and Nonresponse Bias

It is generally believed that CMB is occurred especially when the data collected with questionnaires through survey (Tehseen, Ramayah, & Sajilan, 2017). CMB itself referred to the error of variance divided to the variable and measured items through the same source and method (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, & Podsakoff, 2012). Using Haman Single Factor Test to detect CMB, and claimed that the variant value of less than 50%, to conclude that the research is free from CMB.

Data Analysis and Results

Multivariate analysis deployed to verify the correlation among hypotheses. It was used due to its ability to further analysis the statistic method (J.F. Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2006) and able to offer new insight and further output for research, using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with AMOS 26. This was used as it considered as the suit methodology to complete the research goals. The current study employee large sample as which aligned with the method which can deal with all statistical assumptions (Joseph F. Hair, Risher, Sarstedt, & Ringle, 2019).

This approach is useable in the study which contained of the main multi-item with explorative trait, SEM AMOS delivered a consistency instead of common covariance basis (Chin, 1998). Investigating the relationship among hypotheses, the reliability and validity should be tested at first that considered model measurement (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2019).

The Measurement Model

To measure the Standardized Loading (λ) which is greater than 0,5, Cronbach Alpha (CA) and Composite Reliability (CR) with a range of $\geq 0,5$ as suggested by (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2019). As illustrated at table 2. It highlighted that that CR range of 0,70 to 0,74 and alpha Cronbach range of 0,70 to 0,84. It also demonstrated that all reliability met the cuff-of value is greater than 0,05 (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2019), it also aligned with convergent validity.

Furthermore, Average Variance Extract (EVA) are also found greater than 0,5 for all items and less than 0,5 item loading factor is omitted (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2019).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + e$$

Where;

β_0 - Constant

Y- Dependent variable (Tourism Performance)

X₁= Independent variable (Attitude towards Sustainable tourism strategy)

X₂= Independent variable (Destination Branding)

X₃= Independent variable (Strategy Awareness)

X₄= Independent variable (Cultural Heritage Resources Managed)

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Regression coefficient for each exogenous

Table 2 illustrated the convergent reliability and validity for all constructs, while table 3 summarized the Fornell-Larcker criteria assessment to verify the discriminant validity of constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Aligning with the AVE square value, it must be bigger than all inter-construct correlation (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Table 3 depicted the discriminant validity for all constructs. Table 6 also summarized the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio test to verify and adjust the discriminant validity (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015). Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) should be less than 0,85 (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 2: Reliability and Validity of Constructs

Variable	Indicators	Standardized Loading (λ)	AVE	Alpha (α)	CR
Attitude towards Sustainable tourism strategy	• Awareness of Sustainable Tourism	0,81	.81	.88	.74
	• Perception of Sustainable Tourism	0,80			
	• Support for Sustainable Tourism	0,87			
	• Engagement in Sustainable Tourism	0,79			
Destination Branding	• Recognition	0,67	.75	.78	.76
	• Brand Image	0,69			
	• Perceived Quality	0,68			
	• Appeal	0,85			
	• Reputation	0,85			
Strategy Awareness	• Knowledge of Strategy Objectives	0,75	.70	.74	.72
	• Understanding of Key Components	0,71			
	• Awareness of Stakeholder Roles	0,75			
	• Knowledge of Progress and Updates	0,69			
	• Perceived Importance	0,65			
Cultural Heritage Resources Managed	• Preservation and Conservation	0,58	.72	.74	.70
	• Documentation and Inventory	0,64			
	• Public Accessibility	0,77			
	• Community Engagement	0,83			
	• Sustainability and Adaptation	0,69			
Tourism Performance	• Economic Contribution	0,66	.68	.70	.72
	• Visitor Numbers and Growth	0,72			
	• Sustainability and Environmental Impact	0,58			
	• Community Well-being and Social Impact	0,78			

Source(s): Statistical Output (2023)

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

Construct	1	2	3	4	5
Attitude towards Sustainable tourism strategy	0,84				
Destination Branding	0,75	0,86			
Strategy Awareness	0,73	0,74	0,88		
Cultural Heritage Resources Managed	0,68	0,70	0,79	0,83	
Tourism Performance	0,66	0,69	0,74	0,72	0,85

Source(s): Statistical Output (2023)

Table 4: Discriminant Validity (the HTMT ratio)

Construct	1	2	3	4	5
Attitude towards Sustainable tourism strategy	0,76				
Destination Branding	0,74	0,84			
Strategy Awareness	0,65	0,75	0,88		
Cultural Heritage Resources Managed	0,72	0,77	0,84	0,78	
Tourism Performance	0,67	0,78	0,86	0,84	0,83

Source(s): Statistical Output (2023)

FINDING

Full Structural Model

Present study, which investigate the relationship among Attitude towards Sustainable tourism strategy, Destination Branding, Strategy Awareness, Cultural Heritage Resources Managed on Tourism Performance. Beta value and significant level from all direct and indirect path analysis are estimated as illustrated in table 5.

Table 5: Regression Weights: (Group Number 1 - Default Model)

Hypothesis		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Cultural Heritage Resources	<--- Destination Branding Strategy	,239	,052	4,574	***	par_23
Cultural Heritage Resources	<--- Strategy Awareness	,268	,071	3,764	***	par_24
Cultural Heritage Resources	<--- Attitude towards sustainable tourism strategy	,209	,060	3,482	***	par_26
Tourism Performance	<--- Cultural Heritage Resources	,280	,056	5,040	***	par_22
Tourism Performance	<--- Destination Branding Strategy	,160	,042	3,785	***	par_25
Tourism Performance	<--- Attitude towards sustainable tourism strategy	,164	,046	3,540	***	par_27

Source(s): Statistical Output (2023)

The statistical output demonstrated that the impact of DBS showed a significant impact on Cultural Heritage Resources with CR (4,574). Secondly the impact of Cultural Heritage Resources on Strategy Awareness also showed significant relationship with CR (3,764). The impact of Attitude towards sustainable tourism strategy on Cultural Heritage Resources showed positive relationship with CR (3,482). Cultural Heritage Resources also has a good relationship on tourism performance with CR (5,040). Meanwhile the Destination Branding Strategy and Attitude towards sustainable tourism strategy have a significant impact on tourism performance with CR (3,785; 3,540) respectively. The current complete model shows that Chi-Square = 346, 027 with a freedom degree = 221. $p=0,00$ and $cmin/df$ 1,566. $GFI = 0,928$, $TLI=0,964$, $CFI=0,969$, $IFI=0,969$ and $RMSE = 0,38$, showed that all indicators are met the cut-of value. See the following Fig.5.

Figure 5: Full Structural Model

CONCLUSION

Cultural heritage has some significant implication on tourism destination performance. It could effect on various aspect economy, social, culture as well as environment. The following is the main implication. Firstly, tourism as a source of income. Cultural heritage could be an important asset for destination in case of tourism. Historical sites, museum, cultural festival and others could become the attractiveness which leads on tourism income. This income can be used to build the infrastructures, heritage sustainability and empower local people. With the increased of tourist, cultural heritage sustainability is becoming more important. Government and community should work together to nurture and protect historic sites, old building, art object, and cultural tradition.

This could involve physical maintenance and documentation and education on cultural heritage firstly. Secondly, local economy development. Culture tourism created work opportunity and business opportunity for local people. Souvenir sellers, restaurant and inn as well as other services providers could improve in tourism ecosystem. This also could help to reduce the level

of unemployment and increase living standard in the area. Thirdly, culture promotion and local identity. Culture tourism could help to promote culture and local identity. This will improve the awareness and appreciation on history, art, tradition and local culture. Fourth, management on challenges. Despite the culture tourism could offer much benefits, it could also trigger challenges, over-tourism, environmental damage, excess commercialization. Wise management is required to keep the balance between tourism development and cultural heritage sustainability.

Next, the local community empowerment. Sustainability of cultural tourism should concern on local community empowerment. Local community should engage in decision making, obtain economics benefits, and have access on education opportunity and training needed to involve in tourism industry. Tourism experiences quality, a well maintained cultural heritage could increase tour tourist experiences quality. This will create positive image and in return will attract the revisit intention and recommend to others.

To summarize, cultural heritage has a significant impact on the performance of tourism destination performance. When it well managed, heritages could be priceless assets which could support economy development, cultural reservation, local community development. Yet, it required cultural heritage reservation to be able to offer long term benefits.

Theoretical Implications

Theories related on cultural heritage could offer priceless vision regarding on their implication on tourist destination. Some findings which enrich existed theories are worth to mention such as tourism economy theory, it emphasized the tourism contribution on local economy. In the context of cultural heritage, it implicated that the development and the promotion of cultural heritage could increase local people income, offer job opportunity and support economy growth in the tourism destination. This theory also reminded the important efficient management that maximize the economy benefits.

Secondly, cultural reservation theory, it emphasized on the important to maintain cultural heritage in order to keep its origin due to modernization and development. This is to imply that CH reservation is the prerequisite for long term success in tourism. The destination need to develop policy and effective reservation practices to maintain the cultural integration. Thirdly, social change theory. It reviewed the impact of culture tourism impact on local community. This could lead to positive social changes in society (the increase level of culture awareness and tolerance) or negative impact (cultural commodification or conflict with tourist). Next, sustainability development theory. It emphasized on the need of sustainability development to protect natural resources in the long term.

Destination Management Theory. It focused on tourism management and tourism destination development. In the context of CH, it required well planning, effective marketing and the right tourist management to ensure tourist experience satisfaction and sustainable. Society participation theory, it explored the important of local people in decision making related with tourism and reservation of CH. People with the sense of belonging and engaging with tourism development will more support and ensure the equal benefits. Moreover, the tourist experience

theory. It focused on the experiences and tourist motivation. It implied that tourist experience should be designed to be able to respect and understand cultural value in the destination. The implementation of these theories could help tourism destination organizer to be more effective maximize the positive benefits and reduce negative impact. It is crucial to remember that every tourism destination has their unique traits. Thus, the appropriate approach and customized are needed in integrating these theories in the planning and development of cultural tourism.

Managerial Implication

Managerial implication from CH on tourism destination performance is the need to help to achieve the success and the sustainability in tourism industry. Some implications need to consider such as reservation of management. The destination should allocate sufficient resources to nurture and maintain historical sites, cultural artefacts and other heritages. It could engage on physical maintenance, conservation and documentation maintenance. Secondly, the infrastructures which support the cultural tourism, such as street, public transportation, access for disability, and other supporting facilities. Marketing and promotion.

The destination should develop the right marketing strategy to attract the tourists. This probability to ads campaign, online promotion, participation in tourism exhibition and collaboration with traveling agent. Furthermore, the visitors' management, it is also the important aspect to minimize the negative impact of tourism on CH and environment. It engaged in the tourism quota management, duty hours, tourism guide and others action to maintain CH. Society participation is needed as well in decision making related cultural tourism. Management should create platform the participation which enable community to contribute on the tourism development, sense of belonging, and obtained the benefits from the industry. Training and education. The management should prepare the training and the education for the engaged people in tourism industry such as tourist guide, museum officers, tour operator. This will increase the understanding on cultural heritage and the capability to deliver the quality of tourism experiences. Environmental conservation, tourism management should concern on environment impact. The efforts required is to minimize the carbon track, waste management, nature protection which is nearby of CH.

The effective management of CH required the deeper understanding regarding on cultural value, wise policy, and the commitment to protect and respect the heritages. This also could help to create valuable tourism experience for visitors to ensure CH sustainability for the next generation.

Limitation and Future Studies

Like another fundamental studies, this study also has some limitation. Some are worth to mention is the international respondent and local were grouped in the data analysis. For next study, it is suggested to analyze separately, like doing the multi-group analysis. Secondly, the length of data collection is required since the rate return of respondent is low. For further study, adding and reviewing more variables (city attractiveness, transportation access and others supporting facilities) are recommended to consider.

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